

Methodological quality of ESC/AHA clinical practice guidelines of heart failure across the last two decades: a systematic critical appraisal using the AGREE II Tool.

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Abstract

The article systematically appraises the methodological quality of Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPGs) for heart failure (HF) published by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA) over the past two decades, using the AGREE II tool. The research, conducted by the CONCEPT-HF group, evaluates the evolution of these guidelines' quality to determine improvements in areas like rigor, stakeholder involvement, and clarity.

The study includes 14 CPGs from both the ESC and AHA published between 2000 and 2023. The evaluation process involved a thorough analysis using AGREE II's six domains: Scope and Purpose, Stakeholder Involvement, Rigor of Development, Clarity of Presentation, Applicability, and Editorial Independence. The results showed a steady improvement in methodological quality, with newer guidelines achieving higher scores across all domains.

AHA guidelines improved from a score of 80.4% in 2001 to 94.4% in 2022, while ESC guidelines increased from 79.5% in 2001 to 95% in 2023. The study emphasizes the significant enhancement in stakeholder involvement and editorial independence over time, reflecting better inclusion of various perspectives in guideline development. However, the domain of "Applicability" remains an area where further improvement is necessary, particularly in ensuring the practical implementation of recommendations.

This appraisal demonstrates the continuous refinement of heart failure management guidelines, aiming to improve healthcare outcomes by adhering to robust methodological standards.

Introduction

The management of Heart Failure (HF) is guided by the recommendations of Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPG), systematically developed documents that synthesize all available evidence and shape the care pathway for patients with HF (1). This pathway is understood as the set of actions that the healthcare system must carry out in managing patients, based on the best available evidence, to ensure optimal and quality care.

Globally recognized CPGs for HF, published by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American Heart Association (AHA), have undergone significant transformation over the past two decades, evolving in parallel with the growing understanding of HF. As a result, the current CPGs (2,3) are extensive documents containing numerous recommendations on the diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of patients, which differ significantly from those published in the early 2000s (4,5).

The care pathway derived from CPG recommendations is the concept that the CONCEPT-HF project uses as a reference to analyze the effectiveness of the healthcare process experienced by HF patients. Defining this pathway requires a systematic review of CPGs, with one of the key steps being the evaluation of their methodological quality. While recent studies have assessed the methodological quality of current CPGs (6), their evolution over time has not been analyzed. This research aims to evaluate the evolution of the methodological quality of ESC/AHA CPGs in the management of HF patients over the past 20 years using the AGREE II tool.

Methods

The systematic review, for which this quality analysis of clinical practice guidelines was performed using the AGREE II tool, was conducted in accordance with the 2020 PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) statement, with a protocol registered in PROSPERO (International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews) (CRD42024551462).

The inclusion criteria were clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) published by the ESC and AHA from January 1, 2000, to January 1, 2024, that included recommendations on the management of patients with heart failure, considering only publications in English. Exclusion criteria included clinical practice guidelines developed for non-adult populations, consensus documents, recommendations from scientific societies, or local protocols not published by the ESC or AHA. Systematic reviews and prior meta-analyses were not included in the analysis; however, they were used for backward research to identify articles that could provide primary data.

Sources of Information and Search Strategy

The search was conducted in the following major electronic libraries to obtain available data: PubMed and Scopus. The search strategy used related keywords, Medical Subject Headings (MeSH), and free-text terms for the following concepts: (heart failure) AND (guidelines) AND (European Society of Cardiology) OR (American Heart Association) OR (American College of Chest Physicians) OR (Heart Failure Society). The filters applied to the search strategy were publication date from 01.01.2000 to 01.01.2024.

Study Selection

A standardized summary sheet in MS Excel was created to compile all key data from each study (title, author, abstract, PMID or DOI, and an internally assigned ID) found in the literature search. Several rounds of screening and review were conducted to select all guidelines that met the inclusion criteria. First, after removing all duplicates, two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts of all identified guidelines to assess their eligibility based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria. Any discrepancies between the two primary reviewers (RQ and NJ) were resolved by a third reviewer (EM). Next, a second round of screening was applied. This time, a primary reviewer (FE) carefully read the full articles to precisely determine whether they met the inclusion/exclusion criteria and could be selected for further data extraction.

Quality Assessment of Included Guidelines

A quality assessment of the guidelines was performed to allow for sensitivity analysis based on their quality. This was carried out by two independent reviewers (RQ and NJ) using the AGREE II tool (7). This tool assessed various aspects of guideline design and execution to determine the risk of bias, using the 23 AGREE II items distributed across six domains: Scope and Purpose, Stakeholder Involvement, Rigor of Development, Clarity of Presentation, Applicability, and Editorial Independence. The AGREE II instrument consists of a 7-point response scale, where a score of 1 indicates the lowest quality and 7 indicates the highest quality. Scores between 2 and 6 indicate that the report partially met the criteria according to AGREE II. The scores for each item were summed to obtain a total score for each domain.

Each of these domains was independently evaluated and scored by the two reviewers (RQ, NJ). The evaluation was conducted using the online version "My AGREE PLUS" (AGREE Enterprise website | Advancing the science of practice guidelines (agreetrust.org)), which compiles the scores and comments from the two reviewers. If any individual item had a significant discrepancy (i.e., a difference >2 points), a discussion was held between the two reviewers, mediated by a third reviewer (FE) to reach a consensus. All reviewers' scores were converted into percentages to facilitate understanding and presentation.

The AGREE II tool does not provide formal recommendations on what qualifies as high-quality CPGs; domain scores above 80% are considered high quality, scores between 60% and 79% are considered adequate quality, and scores below 60% are considered low quality (7). Trends in guideline quality over time were interpreted, identifying improvements or setbacks in methodology and applicability of recommendations. The analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 26 for statistical analysis.

Results

Fourteen publications out of the 242 initially identified met the inclusion criteria after full-text review. Seven corresponded to CPGs published by the AHA (2, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12), and the other seven were published by the ESC (3, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 5).

The inter-rater agreement, measured by the Kappa statistic, for the set of 23 questions across the six domains was 0.90 (95% CI: 0.86 to 0.93). In the domain-specific analysis, the Kappa value was consistently above 0.81.

The evolution of the methodological quality of the CPGs over time, based on the scores obtained from the AGREE II evaluation, is reflected in Figure 1, while Figure 2 shows the percentage of the maximum possible score.

Figure 1. Average AGREE II score per year.

CPGs published by the AHA scored a total of 129.5 points in 2001 (80.4%), increasing to 153 points (94.4%) in the 2022 guidelines. For CPGs published by the ESC, they scored 128 points in 2001 (79.5%), rising to 153 points (95%) in 2023.

Figure 2. Total score obtained, expressed as a percentage of the maximum possible, in the overall score of the AGREE II tool.

The evolution of the domain-specific scores for AHA CPGs in the AGREE II assessment is presented in Figure 3. Comparing the first and most recent guidelines (from 2001 to 2023), the progression was as follows: Domain 1 [Scope and Purpose]: 17.5→21 points (maximum score: 21), Domain 2 [Stakeholder Involvement]: 14→19.5 points (maximum score: 21), Domain 3 [Rigor of Development]: 47.5→54 points (maximum score: 56), Domain 4 [Clarity of Presentation]: 20→21 points (maximum score: 21), Domain 5 [Applicability]: 18.5→23.5 points (maximum score: 28), Domain 6 [Editorial Independence]: 12→14 points (maximum score: 14).

Figure 3. Evolution of the score obtained in each of the domains of the AGREE II tool in the clinical practice guidelines published by the AHA.

Figure 4. Evolution of the score obtained in each of the domains of the AGREE II tool in the clinical practice guidelines published by the ESC.

Figure 4 shows the scores obtained for ESC CPGs. Comparing the changes between 2001 and 2023, the evolution was as follows: Domain 1 [Scope and Purpose]: 17→21 points (maximum score: 21), Domain 2 [Stakeholder Involvement]: 13.5→20 points (maximum score: 21), Domain 3 [Rigor of Development]: 47.5→54 points (maximum score: 56), Domain 4 [Clarity of Presentation]: 19.5→21 points (maximum score: 21), Domain 5 [Applicability]: 18.5→22.5 points (maximum score: 28), Domain 6 [Editorial Independence]: 12→14 points (maximum score: 14).

Discussion

Our results show a progressive improvement in the quality of the evaluated CPGs, with notable increases in all domains of the AGREE II evaluation, reflecting a continuous effort to improve the methodological rigor and applicability of recommendations in the management of HF. These findings are consistent with recent studies (6), where improvements in the methodological quality of more recent CPGs were also observed.

The agreement between the evaluators was excellent, with a Kappa value higher than 0.81 in all domains, indicating great consistency in the evaluations performed. This high level of agreement reinforces the reliability of the evaluation process and suggests that the ESC and AHA guidelines have been developed following homogeneous criteria and have well-defined methodologies. This aligns with the findings of Saphien et al., who also found a high level of agreement between evaluators, with a Kappa value of 0.80 (95% CI: 0.72 to 0.89) for the 23 questions across the 6 domains (6).

The evolution of both European and American CPGs shows an increase in overall quality, as seen in Figure 1; these improvements reflect not only the continuous update of recommendations based on new scientific evidence but also a greater focus on key aspects such as stakeholder involvement and clarity in the presentation of recommendations, both of which are essential for effective clinical implementation. This increase in quality is consistent with previous studies that highlight the importance of these factors. For example, Brouwers et al. (7) emphasize that clarity of presentation and stakeholder involvement, including patients and other relevant actors, play a crucial role in ensuring that guidelines are understandable and applicable in daily clinical practice. Moreover, a study by Kung et al. (18) highlighted that higher-quality guidelines tend to involve a wider range of stakeholders, which not only facilitates the acceptance of recommendations but also their adaptation to diverse clinical contexts.

The improvement in these domains allows the guidelines not only to provide recommendations based on solid evidence but also to be accessible and feasible for healthcare professionals, thus enhancing implementation and adherence in daily practice. However, it is important to note that AGREE II evaluates

the quality of the documentation provided in the guidelines and the process used for their development, but it does not necessarily assess the clinical-epidemiological value of the recommendations themselves, which are generally accepted as valid. Nevertheless, as we know, they should not always be taken for granted, as the evidence may vary in its applicability and relevance depending on the clinical or epidemiological context in which they are implemented. This underscores the need to continue evaluating guidelines not only from a methodological standpoint but also in terms of their effectiveness and applicability across different populations and settings.

Of particular note is the increase in the "Stakeholder Involvement" domain, in both AHA and ESC guidelines, indicating greater inclusion of patients and other actors in the development of the guidelines, thus promoting greater representativeness and transparency in the decision-making process. Other studies have also found that the representation of patients as panel members remains an area with room for improvement, as only two of the guidelines included in their analysis explicitly mentioned the inclusion of patient representatives (19). Similarly, the "Rigor of Development" domain has shown significant improvements, suggesting greater attention to methodological quality and the robustness of the recommendations issued.

Nevertheless, some domains, such as "Applicability," remain areas where further improvements can still be made. Although advances were observed in this aspect, scores in this domain are still below the maximum possible score, indicating that the guidelines face significant challenges regarding the practical implementation of their recommendations. This domain evaluates the ease with which recommendations can be implemented in clinical practice, considering factors such as the necessary resources, economic impact, and adaptability to different healthcare settings (20). These findings are consistent with those of Saphien et al., who reported that applicability remains one of the weakest areas, with an average score of 43% in their analysis.

Moreover, applicability is directly related to the ability of healthcare systems to effectively adopt the recommendations. This may include the availability of infrastructure, access to advanced technologies, or even financial constraints, especially in resource-limited settings. Regional differences in access to medications, diagnostic procedures, or trained personnel may make some recommendations difficult to fully implement, creating a gap between what the guidelines suggest and what is feasible in practice (1). Another relevant barrier that may be influencing the scores in this domain is the lack of clear strategies for the evaluation of costs and resources, a crucial aspect for public health decision-making. Only a minority of the guidelines analyzed incorporate explicit assessments of the cost-effectiveness of their recommendations, making it difficult for decision-makers to balance clinical effectiveness with economic

sustainability (21). Consequently, the guidelines may be less useful for health managers when prioritizing interventions in contexts with budgetary constraints.

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. First, although strict inclusion and exclusion criteria were used to select the clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) evaluated, the analysis was limited to guidelines published by the ESC and AHA, potentially excluding other relevant CPGs from other regions or scientific societies that could have provided a broader perspective on methodological quality. Second, although the AGREE II tool is widely used and validated, its application depends largely on the subjectivity of the evaluators, which may introduce some degree of bias in the scoring of the domains. Although measures were taken to mitigate this issue, such as the involvement of a third evaluator in cases of significant discrepancies, some interpretations may vary according to the personal judgment of the reviewers (22). Additionally, this study did not assess the real clinical impact of the CPGs in daily practice, limiting our ability to directly relate methodological quality to patient health outcomes (23). Finally, the exclusion of guidelines not published in English may have limited the diversity of the analyzed guidelines and, therefore, the generalizability of the findings to other geographical and linguistic contexts.

In conclusion, this analysis highlights the favorable evolution of the methodological quality of HF CPGs from the ESC and AHA over the past two decades, with consistent improvements in all domains evaluated by AGREE II. However, future guidelines should continue to emphasize the practical applicability of their recommendations to ensure that methodological advances translate into tangible improvements in patient care.

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List of abbreviations:

AHA: American Heart Association

AGREE II: Appraisal of Guidelines for Research and Evaluation II

CPG: Clinical Practice Guidelines

ESC: European Society of Cardiology

HF: Heart Failure

PRISMA: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Our research project adheres to the ethical principles applicable to this type of study as outlined in the Helsinki Declaration. The handling of personal data of participants complies with the provisions of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of April 27, 2016, and Organic Law 3/2018 of December 5, on the Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights, as well as adhering to standards of good clinical practice. As such, it has obtained approval from the Coordinating Committee on Biomedical Research Ethics in Andalusia in April, 27th 2021 meeting (Acta 04/21) with PEIBA registry id: 0088-N-21.

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Availability of data and materials

All aggregated datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study will be available from the corresponding author on reasonable request. Any other digital objects generated by CONCEPT-HF, such as its common data model, synthetic data, analytical pipeline, results from the data quality analyses, etc. will be published under a CC-BY 4.0 International license in Zenodo.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

RQ – drafting of the article, independent evaluation of CPGs using the AGREE II tool, and planning of the analysis.

FE – drafting of the article, creation of the data summary sheet, full-text review of the included CPGs, and planning of the analysis methodology.

EB - article revision, design of the CONCEPT project, and analysis methodology.

EM – third reviewer in the evaluation process, responsible for resolving discrepancies between the primary reviewers.

NJ – drafting of the article, independent evaluation of CPGs using the AGREE II tool, article revision, and participation in resolving discrepancies in the CPG evaluation.

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